

English in the early years of elementary school at public schools in Brazil: a study of two teacher's beliefs about the teacher and learning process

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ABSTRACT: *In this paper we intend to identify the beliefs of two English teachers for kids at public school about the teaching and learning process of foreign language. As theoretical background we discuss theories concerning beliefs on foreign language teaching and learning and, we also discuss aspects of teaching English for kids and the official documents that standardize the insertion of a foreign language at curriculum of basic education. The methodology adopted was a qualitative case study. The participants of the study were two English teachers for kids, and to generate data we used questionnaires, interviews, narratives and also the activities and lesson plans elaborated by the teachers. The results of this research suggest that the teachers have three distinct beliefs about English language learning: 1) general beliefs about teaching English for kids; 2) beliefs about the role of English teacher for kids; and 3) beliefs about the elaboration and material use for teaching English for kids.*

KEYWORDS: *beliefs, English for kids, teaching and learning process, public school.*

I. INTRODUCTION

In context of basic education, teaching foreign language is organized by official documents that guide teaching and, according to these papers, the insertion of foreign language only happens in the final years of fundamental education and in high school. In this perspective, the universities prepare the teachers to act in the phases of basic education. And as we know teaching English for kids that is in a significative growth represents a gap in teachers' initial education.

Consequently, the teachers who will work with kids, direct their teaching based on what they believe will functionate in their classroom. To Barcelos (1995) [3] beliefs are related to how people reflect about their previous experiences. Thus, according to this statement, teachers work having in mind what they know about their education in undergraduate coursed, and what they use to work in other groups of students.

In addition, Freeman and Jonhson (1998) [13] claim that the teachers' beliefs are essential in their professional qualification, once their knowledge and their conceptions about teaching and learning process are part of their background as teachers.

The objective of this study is to identify and discuss English teachers' beliefs for kids about the teaching and learning process in public school scope. In this context, it is important to mention that there was not a qualification period for the professional in order to teach kids, just their beliefs. To do this, we conducted a qualitative case study like suggested by Esteban, 2010 [11] and Yin, 2005 [33] in which we interviewed the

teachers, analyzed their lesson plans, their activities and the narratives that they wrote seeking to understand their beliefs and its influences on teachers' practice at classroom.

This paper is organized the following way. First, we discuss some documents that standardized the teaching of foreign language in basic education schools, following by concepts related to beliefs about teaching and learning. Then, we discuss the methodology adopted in this study and, in the end, we present the results derived from the data analysis and present some final remarks.

II. TEACHING ENGLISH FOR KIDS

Learning a foreign language gives the students the opportunity to have contact with a new language and a new culture different from their own and, in this way, the insertion of this language in basic education curriculum is important. Important documents that guide EFL at public and private schools in Brazil are, for example, *Lei de Diretrizes e Bases da Educação (LDB)*, and *Parâmetros Curriculares Nacionais*, among others. Exemplifying these documents, the *Lei de Diretrizes e Bases da Educação*, in its article 24, suggests that "classes can be organized, with students from different stages, with equivalent levels of subject advance, to teaching of foreign languages, arts, or another curricular component" (LDB, 2017, p. 18) [10]. Therefore, teaching a foreign language had a higher influence after *LDB* in high school that today represents the basic education, and it in charge of the institutions the insertion of this foreign language in the school curriculums.

In 1996, a new version of *LDB* was published and it brought the obligatoriness of teaching a foreign language from 5th grade of elementary school, that today represents the 6th grade, and in high school emerged. Besides that, the document suggests that a second foreign language should be offered to the students, at the discretion and within the possibilities of the institution. According to the document, "in the curriculum of elementary school, from sixth grade, the English language will be offered" (LDB, 2017, p. 20) [10].

From this obligatoriness *LDB* suggests that English teaching in basic schools, appear in 1998 the *Parâmetros Curriculares Nacionais (PCNs)*, that standardized the contents that should be taught in final years of elementary school and also the *PCNEM* in 2000, that standardized the contents that should be taught in high school, likewise the *PNC+* also directed to this group.

In a general way, teaching foreign languages at basic education is firm by *Base Nacional Comum Curricular* of 2013, and it is up to the institution to choose this foreign language, being able to choose the Spanish language (BRASIL, 2013) [9], obligatorily from 6th grade of elementary school.

Recently, a document that renew the *Base Nacional Comum Curricular (BNCC)* still emphasizes that teaching foreign languages is only in the final years of fundamental education and in high school. According to the document, the early years of basic education are directed to children literacy without even mentioning the possibility of teaching a foreign language in this stage. According to *BNCC* the first two years of schooling is to children's literacy.

In view of this, according to *BNCC*, learning how to read and how to write will provide the students with the construction of knowledge, in order to effectively and socioculturally participate in several literate practices, in a way to emphasize the literacy process of these individuals. However, as can be noted previously on this paper, the insertion of a foreign language only will start from the final years of elementary school. In addition, the document shows that "in Fundamental Education – Final Years, the learning, in the curricular components of this area, expand the language practices achieve in Elementary School – Early Years, including the English language learning". (BRASIL, 2018, p. 64) [8].

Based on legislation that organized foreign language teaching at basic education in Brazil, the teacher formation in undergraduation has focus on these documents and is directed towards acting on final grades of elementary school and high school like the official documents suggest. In this sense, teaching English on first grades makes teachers search for a continuing courses, as Santos explains (2002) [30], whereas the university does not offer allowances for teachers to work with children in first grades of elementary school.

In basic education, even not contemplated on teaching education process, EFL for children became a reality to these teachers of the languages area, whereas official documents guiding English teaching in both

public and private schools do not provide the insertion of a foreign language in the first years of elementary school. In this way, the initial teaching education at university of these professors has a crucial role in their knowledge and in their practices at classroom (ALMEIDA FILHO, 1999 [1]; LEFFA, 2008 [8]).

The courses of *Letras*, even *Letras: Inglês*, *Letras: Português/Inglês* or *Letras: Português/Inglês e suas respectivas literaturas*, give rise to the teacher education with focus on linguistic, on foreign language and on its literatures, and allows teachers to act in the final grades of fundamental education and high school, corroborating the norms of the official documents that guide teaching on basic education. Instead, these courses do not offer to professionals, subjects aimed to children, consequently a lack of teaching methodologies in order to work with kids occurs in this context.

In the other hand, the *Pedagogia* course offers training to professionals that will work with the first grades of elementary school and in the child education. Like this, the professional will have as focus the literacy process of the students, regardless of the disciplines that will be offered to them such as English. At most, these subjects are offered as an optional basis in higher education curriculum.

Hence, the professional of *Letras*' courses does not have preparation to teach foreign languages to kids and, thus, take this role. In this way, teachers work in this stage of elementary school based on that they believe, according to Félix (1999) [12]. In Félix's words, teachers "when go to their classrooms, or when they act as professionals before, they start to act guided to a certainly teaching approach" (FÉLIX, 1999, p. 94) [12].

From this perspective, beliefs on teacher education imbricate and became fundamental in this process, once the professional, when inserted in the classroom context without initial education for pedagogical practice, uses what they believe that can work in class.

In the next section, we present the aspects of teacher's beliefs regardless the teaching and learning process of a foreign language.

III. BELIEFS ABOUT LANGUAGE TEACHING AND LEARNING

According to Barcelos (2004) [5], the studies concerning beliefs started to gain visibility in Brazil in 1990. The author presents a table using several definitions and terms that underlines the construct beliefs since the 90s to the present. As Barcelos (2004) [5] argues, some of these terms and definitions refer to, for example, representations (RILEY, 1989) [29], cultural beliefs (GARDNER, 1988) [14], beliefs about language teaching and learning (BARCELOS, 1995) [3], among others. However, in this paper, we will adopt the term suggested by Barcelos (1995), despite the multiplicity that this construct can present.

For Barcelos (2004) [5], the term beliefs about language learning appears in 1985 on Applied Linguistics, when BALLI (Beliefs About Language Learning Inventory), a tool used to find beliefs from teachers and students in a systematic way, idealized by Horwitz (1985) [15]. Soon, in Brazil, according to the author, the term arises and gain visibility from huge theoretical landmarks as Leffa (1991) [19], Almeida Filho (1993) [2] and Barcelos (1995) [3] researches.

In this perspective, beliefs are related to how people deal and absorb their reality, and, in this way, can reflect about previous personal experiences, readings, and contact with other people, like Barcelos suggests (1995) [3]. Regarding to this, we can understand that teacher's beliefs can influence their practices at classroom, because they will use what they believe, reflecting on this their knowledge and, in consequence, their beliefs like suggest (BARCELOS, 1995 [3], 1999 [4], 2010 [7]; PAJARES, 1992 [26]; SILVA, 2000 [31]), among others.

Analyzing teachers' beliefs, Johnson (1994) [17] claims that these beliefs represents important influences in the way teachers think, understand their context and act in it. However, according to the author, little focus has been given to the origins of these beliefs and how they emerge from teachers' reality in everyday classroom. Concerning teacher education and the manner how beliefs are intrinsic on teacher's practice, Horwitz (1998) [16] states that in studying teachers' beliefs, the focus is not on judging whether those beliefs are positive or negative, whether they are right or wrong, but rather to check and discuss its impact on the students' learning process.

Several researchers conduct their studies based on beliefs, both focused on teachers' (BARCELOS, 2004 [5]; OLIVEIRA; LAGO, 2012 [25]) and learners' (BARCELOS, 2010 [7]; LAGO; CINTRA, 2016 [18]; RICHARDS; LOCKART, 1996 [28]) and also related to emotions (BARCELOS, 2007 [6], 2010 [7]; FREEMAN; JONHSON, 1998 [13]). Regarding to this, although there is a growing influence of beliefs in education about teachers' practices at classroom that direct teaching and learning process, some authors still point out the need for greater breadth in these discussions, like Martini (2003) [21] suggests. And, in this way, on this growing context of teaching English for kids, studies on teachers' beliefs about foreign language teaching and learning becomes pertinent.

IV. THE STUDY

This research is characterized as a qualitative case study (ESTEBAN, 2010 [11]; YIN, 2005 [33]). For Yin (2005, p. 32) [33], this kind of research "is an empiric investigation that searches a phenomenon inside its real-life context". According to Nunan (1992) [24], when we adopt a case study as methodology, we have the opportunity to investigate one individual, or a group of these individuals, as in the case of this study.

The investigation was conducted with two English teachers for children at public school context. To elucidate the participants of this study, we present some academic and professional information about them. In order to ensure the privacy of these participants, we used the pseudonyms Emma and Fiona, chosen by themselves.

Emma is an English teacher since 2004 and always worked in a public educational context. She has a degree in *Letras: Português/Inglês e suas respectivas literaturas* by *Universidade Estadual de Goiás* and has a master degree in *Letras e Linguística* by *Universidade Federal de Goiás*. Since she started her career as a teacher, Emma has taught students in final years of elementary school (6th to 9th grades) and in high school. Only from 2010 she started to teach children and, in 2018, she had her first experience in teaching English for kids in literacy process.

Fiona is an English teacher since 2010 and she works only in a public educational context nowadays, however, she had had experience in language courses. She has degree in *Letras: Português/Inglês* by *Universidade Salgado de Oliveira* and she is a master's student in *Ensino na Educação Básica* by *Universidade Federal de Goiás*. From the beginning of her career as a teacher, she had worked with kids and teens at private schools, and from 2012, she began teaching children in public schools.

The tools we used to collect data were questionnaires, as well as interviews and two narratives. We also analyzed their lesson plans and some kind of activities elaborated by Emma and Fiona.

Moreira and Caleffe (2008) [22] state that interviews are very important and rich instruments to generate data and, according to them using these tools, the participants can answer the questions and can express themselves better, contrasting with questionnaires. In this way, the interviews were used to obtain information about the participants' education process at university and about their beliefs and their practice in classroom.

The narratives, in turn, were used to retrieve, through participants' reports, information highlighting their point of view about teaching English to kids. As Telles (1999) [32] suggests, this instrument can illustrate the life, professional and social experiences of the participants, and finally, the lesson plans and the activities were used to illustrate Emma and Fiona's practice in the classroom.

V. DATA DISCUSSION

The data generated through the questionnaires, the interviews and the narratives answered by Emma and Fiona about their beliefs allowed data triangulation and directed the analysis into three distinct categories. These categories were divided into subsections named as 1) general beliefs about teaching English for kids; 2) beliefs about the role of English teacher for kids; and 3) beliefs about the elaboration and material use for teaching English for kids.

1) General beliefs about teaching English for kids

As we discussed at the theoretical framework in this paper, teaching English for kids is a reality for teachers and it is growing at public schools. Thus, in addition to the classes of early years of elementary school that had recently introduced English as a foreign language (4th and 5th grades) into their curriculum, literacy classes also had inserted English in their curriculum recently.

In this perspective, teachers guide their work based on their beliefs about foreign language teaching and learning process. So, through the interviews and narratives analysis, we can understand that the teachers have beliefs that means: a) teaching English for kids is difficult in literacy process; b) teachers need to keep students in attention at class using visual and playful resources.

As for the first belief, we can note in the following excerpt by Emma who claims that teaching English for kids is important, however, she believes that English, taught in the same time as children's first language (in this case Portuguese), can hinder their literacy process, as we can see in this interview excerpt:

I see that teaching English for kids is an important thing, because the child has this contact, you know, since small. But it is complicated because in the university we don't have formation to work in this phase and so we are out of action when we have to work with kids. And when they are in literacy process it is more complicated, because I believe that when the child is in literacy process of their mother tongue and they have to learn also English, it can cause some difficult to them in this process. And because of this, I always use Portuguese in my classes. (Interview excerpt from Emma).

In this excerpt Emma also highlight that, in her classes, she constantly uses students' first language, because she was afraid of the confusion that may be created in students' literacy process. Concerning this, we can understand that this belief expressed by Emma corroborates Johnson's ideas (1994) [17] when he claims that teachers perceive and act based on what they believe to be important to students.

Contrary to what Emma thoughts, Fiona see that teaching English for kids is extremally important and also claims that in the context that the kids are inserted makes them have contact with the language. The teacher suggests that communication in English is so important to children's life and in their school formation.

I believe that English is extremally important to the kids, first because English is the language from the videos that they watch, from the cartoons, from the games, from the music, from the toys among other things that are in their daily life. Second, because English language is important to their academic life and also it is another way for them to communicate and express themselves. (Narrative excerpt from Fiona).

In the following narrative excerpt from Emma, we identify another belief from the teacher: she believes that she needs always stays to alert to bring to the class playful tools to facilitate kids' comprehension of English language.

In my lesson plans, I always bring to my classes activities that will make my students pay attention, especially when they are very young, because it's so hard to work with kids and make them participate with attention in the activities that I propose to them. So, I think that bringing the TV to the classroom and put on it a DVD with videos in English, with music, with a lot of visual information can help me in this challenge of keep my students attentive in the classes. Sometimes it works and the class happens quietly, but sometimes it is a little more complicated because kids are very enthusiastic and then you have to turn off the television and they don't like it. (Narrative excerpt from Emma).

Here we can note again that the teacher's action in her classes is based on what she believes that will be efficient, as Johnson (1994) [17] suggests. Also, according to Barcelos (2004) [5], the beliefs that teachers have can, thus, influence their practices. To exemplify one of these Emma's activities using TV and DVD, we show a sort of her lesson plan.

Time: 01 h/a week

Content: Numbers

Specific objectives:

- Recognize the numbers in English;
- Use vocabulary learnt in communicative situations.

Time:	Procedures:	Tools:
1-10	Brainstorm Review with students the numbers from 1 to 5 that they have learnt and give to them instructions for the class.	White board.
10-55	Video Show to students an English video about the numbers.	TV and DVD.
55-60	Follow up... Finish the work with numbers from 1 to 5 and give directions to the next class.	

Source: Emma's lesson plan.

We can note in this sort of lesson plan that Emma elaborates her plans in a simple way and justifies it because she has a lot of class for week and, in this way, she found a way to plan her classes in order to make her job easier. In this lesson plan we can note that the teacher uses the TV and the DVD as a way of bringing to the class a review of the content that she worked on and, like Emma said in her narrative, she used these tools in order to keep students attentive in class.

In Emma's lesson plans, besides realizing the care that she has to bring to class playful moments to her students, she also contextualizes these moments with the content or to work with cultural aspects of children's reality. Emma also tries to relate in her classes Brazilian and English-speaking countries cultural aspects, as we can note in another sort of Emma's lesson plan.

Time: 2h/a

Content: Sports; June Party; Text Comprehension; Grammatical aspects.

Specific objectives:

- Learn vocabulary related to sports;
- Relate holidays in Brazil and in United States;
- Read and understand short texts;
- Use vocabulary in communicative situations.

1st class

Time:	Procedures:	Tools:
1-5	Brainstorm Present to students the content of the class: June Party.	White board.
5-60	Video In this class students will watch videos related to a party that occurs in June and then work with its cultural aspects.	TV and DVD.

2nd class

Time:	Procedures:	Tools:
1-10	Brainstorm Present to students the content of the class: June Party.	White board; marker; informal talk with students.
10-50	Activity Handout to fixation of vocabulary and cultural aspects that students have learnt about June Party.	Handout.
50-60	Follow up... Review the aspects that students learnt in this class and finalization of classes of June.	Informal talk with students.

Source: Emma's lesson plan.

In the following section we discuss the second belief that emerged from the data analysis in this study: how teachers see their role as English teachers for kids at public schools.

2) Beliefs about the role of English teacher for kids

The teacher education at university is fundamental for their significant exercise as teachers, and according to Almeida Filho (1999) [1] and Leffa (2008) [20], it is also important to the construction of their knowledge and in their act at classroom. However, a barrier is built when these teachers start to teach in grades that they do not received formation to do this and, thus, start to act according to what they believe.

In this way, the participants' beliefs in this study suggest that children only learn if teachers motivate them and keep them attentive in classes, as can be noted in the following interview excerpt from Emma.

I see my role as teacher as a person who has to motivate my students to learn, you know? To make them pay attention in my classes and do the activities in the right way, but, besides that, I have to keep in mind that I also have to control my class, control the mess, because children always want to play, jump, sing, and sometimes people outside the classroom see this as a bad thing, they think that I'm not working, I'm not teaching, and so on. (Interview excerpt from Emma).

According to the teacher, she sees her role as a person who has to make students attentive to not disperse in the classes and, in this way, they can understand the content that they're learning. Besides that, Emma also mentions that the fact that she is always trying to make students keep attention has to do with maintaining classroom organization and students' behavior during the activities and this corroborate what Nespor (1987) [23] indicates in discussing affective aspects of beliefs.

From the standpoint of Nespor (1987) [23] who presents the affective aspects of beliefs, we found in the following Fiona's narrative her need in motivate her students, arousing in them commitment and responsibility as learners of a foreign language.

My role at classroom as a teacher is motivate the children to learn English language showing them that English is so important because it is on their daily life. Besides motivating and showing the importance of English, I believe that my role is also to develop in my students notions of commitment, responsibility, autonomy, persistency and dedication with the learning process. Besides all of this, my role is mediate students' knowledge and also collaborate with them in this process. (Narrative excerpt from Fiona).

Like Fiona, Emma also believes that it is fundamental that teachers motivate children to participate in classes, as we can see in the following excerpt.

As I said, I think that we as teachers should keep our students motivated, you know, create on them the conscious about the importance of studying English, because English is everywhere around them and when they are very young I believe that we need to motivate them a lot. So, I try to use this justification to make them more motivated. (Narrative excerpt from Emma).

To Emma, motivation is essential in the classroom and especially when we talk about children, because they need more attention and they also need more motivation to do the activities proposed to them.

In the following interview excerpt, Fiona mentions the importance of her role as an English teacher for kids.

I haven't really had an education, a training for teaching English for children, but I believe that my role as a teacher is to seek to adapt materials, to understand their context and make my best in teaching English meaningfully for them, you know, for them use at least orally and listen, because in these stages they don't know how to write or read [...] I make use of videos, of images, cartoons, music, so they can be interested in the language, and to be able to really arouse interest in the English language and make them use it in some way, even in repetition. (Interview excerpt from Fiona).

As we can see, Fiona even not having training to teach kids, believes that she has a fundamental role in this process and search for solutions to teach her students. We note that the teacher elaborates her own material and try to bring more meaningful teaching to her students.

Throughout the narratives and interviews excerpts and corroborating with Félix's (1999) [12] words that the teacher acts based on a given teaching approach, we can understand that Fiona and also Emma use this conception when they are preparing their own material and making use of resources that they believe will have an effective and significant result to their students, like suggests Johnson (1994) [17].

In the next subsection, we discuss the last of the three beliefs that emerged in the narratives and interviews answered by Fiona and Emma and that are related to how they elaborate and use their own material to teach English for kids.

In this subsection, we also bring some sort of the material that the teachers elaborate to use with the children.

3) Beliefs about the elaboration and material use for teaching English for kids

Based on the assumption that Emma and Fiona did not have formation to teach English for kids and even that they assumed this role, they started to work based on what they believe will be efficient for the teaching and learning process. Furthermore, the teachers need to create their own material, since the public education context does not offer books and/or materials for this audience. So, in the following excerpt, taken from Fiona's narrative, we can note that the teacher declares herself as an eclectic teacher in relation to approaches and materials that she uses in her classes.

I'm extremely eclectic in all areas of my life. In professional life it would not be different. I use methods that work. If in my class the Grammar-Translation Method works, so I use it, for example: when I need to present new vocabulary or group of words, I can work with this method, asking them to

look at figures (flashcards) and write in their notebooks and then we search in the dictionary. When I realize that I need to use a method with another, I use. Usually, I try to use a communicative approach, because I defend and believe that the language should be learnt to communication. But I don't see problems in using several approaches. To do this, I evaluate the behavior and learning styles from my students and then I reflect about the approach that will be better to each activity or content. (Narrative excerpt from Fiona).

As we can see in Fiona's narrative, the teacher acts according to her previous knowledge and, also, guided by some sort of teaching and learning approaches that she believes will work in her classroom, corroborating to Félix's (1998) [12] words.

In the other hand, Emma sees the role of the material that she develops as a tool to hold student's time because, as mentioned by her, she needs to keep the students attentive to the classes and to the activities. Thus, she seeks to create her material using many pictures, so the students spend part of their time painting and quiet, as we can see in the following excerpt.

As I have difficult in working with kids, I try to bring to classes materials that keep them in attention, you know? So, I bring many paintings, of course all of them are contextualized with the subject that I'm teaching. I believe that in this way they can have a better assimilation from the vocabulary that I taught to them and also, they get less agitated, because I have two hours class twice a week in each grade, so this is so much time. (Interview excerpt from Emma).

We can understand, based on this interview excerpt, that Emma elaborates her material having in mind what she believes, like Johnson (1994) [17] and Barcelos (2010) [7] suggest. In this case, in a sort of activity that will keep students more attentive in classes and not disperse too much. As an example of the material adapted by Emma, we have here an activity about numbers and colors that she gave to 6 years students.

COLORS

Source: RADESPIEL; RADESPIEL, 2010 [27].

In this activity, we can see the teachers' care of working in a playful way using the content that she taught in class (colors and numbers). Hence, like she points out, we can understand that the picture used by her on this activity is big in order to keep her students working a long time during the class. Fiona, for instance, has a wide scope regarding the materials that she elaborates and uses with her students as we can see in the following interview excerpt.

All the material that I use I adapted them, I create flashcards, I use projector, I always use images, videos, to teach significantly to my students. I use handouts, flashcards, I play with them in the board, I always try to adapt to their reality. When they don't know how to write and read, I use figures, even if I put this picture in front of them, I use more images with kids, and videos. (Interview excerpt from Fiona).

We can note that Fiona elaborates her material based on what she believes that will work and that will bring benefits to her students and consequently make them understand the language. Fiona also points out her awareness about using visual tools in her activities when she has to work with kids that do not know how to write and read yet.

As we have seen, through both narratives and interviews answered by the teachers, we can understand that Fiona and Emma plan their classes, their activities and materials according to their beliefs about foreign language teaching and learning, corroborating to the Pajares (1992) [26] and Jonhson (1994) [17] considerations by stating that these beliefs that teachers have are built throughout their lives and their careers as teachers, that is, from their own experiences.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study allowed us to conclude about the importance of teaching English for kids that has been taking a wide range in all spheres of education, whether public or private and, especially, on how teachers act in classroom when they do not have initial education at university to deal with this teaching context.

In this perspective, regarding the analysis that we have done on this paper, we can understand that the beliefs teachers have about language teaching and learning and also about their experiences on grades of the final years of elementary school are essential to them in doing this work.

Therefore, the English teachers' beliefs for kids have shown here help these teachers while they plan their classes, while they elaborate their materials and activities and then adapt them to the children' context and, in this way, offers to kids significantly language learning.

However, is important to think in other and new perspectives for this field of education in university courses, because every day more and more teachers are starting teaching English for kids and, in this way, a directed education to this public is extremely important in teachers' education process.

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